

Coastal flood hazard for Lecce, Italy, from breaches in the dunes

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ABSTRACT

The territory of the municipality of Lecce encompasses a long coastal strip along the Adriatic Sea, which, to date, lacks high-resolution flood hazard mapping. We used a 1-m-resolution digital terrain model (DTM), as well as extreme sea level (ESL) projections from the literature, including storm surge, wave setup, tide, and mean sea level rise. A geodetic transformation was used to refer ESL to the DTM vertical datum. The outcome was used in a bathtub model, validated via *in situ* photos and satellite observations. The modest elevation and gentle slope of the terrain lead to a potential long-range flooding. The northern sectors, including Spiaggiabella, Torre Chianca, and a specific site in Frigole, are identified as the areas most susceptible to coastal flooding. Gaps and damage to the dune belt, specific roads, and reclamation canals can function as ingress points for seawater during flooding events. While the results are affected by several uncertainties, we find an appreciable coastal hazard for several urban and agricultural settlements in Lecce. The study underscores the importance of territorial monitoring in shaping effective, context-specific adaptation strategies for coastal resilience along the Lecce shoreline.

Key words: bathtub, coastal, dunes, flooding, geoid, sea level rise

HIGHLIGHTS

- First hazard mapping for coastal flooding along the coastal strip of Lecce.
- Based on a high-resolution terrain model and extreme sea level projections.
- Damage to the dune belt as entry points for flooding.
- The floodable territory has been characterized by land cover type.
- Preliminary validation via *in situ* photos and satellite imagery.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

GLOSSARY

AdriaClim	'Climate change information, monitoring and management tools for adaptation strategies in Adriatic coastal areas', a project of the 2014–2020 Interreg V-A Italy-Croatia CBC Programme
AdriaClimPlus	follow-up of the AdriaClim project
BTM	bathtub model
CLC	Corine land cover
CORDEX	Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment
DTM	digital terrain model
ESL	extreme sea level
FEMA	Federal Emergency Management Agency
FES	finite element solution
HDM	hydrodynamic model
Med-CORDEX	contribution to CORDEX for the Mediterranean region
MSL	mean sea level
NDWI	Normalized Difference Water Index
POI	places of interest (a set of landmarks from the Lecce PUG's draft)
PUG	Piano Urbanistico Generale (Urban Master Plan)
qGIS	formerly 'quantum GIS', a geographic information system
RCP	representative concentration pathway
RMSE	root mean square error
S2GLC	Sentinel-2 global land cover
SP133	Strada Provinciale (provincial road) no. 133

1. INTRODUCTION

Coastal urban communities face rising risks exacerbated by climate change. Rapid urbanization, pressure from tourism and maritime transport, pollution, coastal erosion, sea level rise, storm surges, and saltwater intrusion are stressors affecting both the coastal environment and human activities (Davenport & Davenport 2006). Several studies have underscored the complex interplay between sea level variability and its cascading effects on coastal communities, emphasizing the importance of data-

driven analyses in understanding and mitigating coastal flooding risks. In Venice, [Ferrarin *et al.* \(2022\)](#), from the analysis of over 140 years of *in situ* observations, found a significant increase in nuisance flooding, with tide and long-term fluctuations, attributed to both subsidence and sea level rise, becoming dominant factors. [Li *et al.* \(2021\)](#) reported a sharp rise in tidal flooding events along the United States coastline since 1950, driven not only by tidal changes but also by rising mean sea levels. Indeed, an enhancement of coastal flood risk is expected because of sea level rise ([Hinkel & Klein 2009](#)). The Japan Meteorological Agency¹ offers an operational mapping service for various types of geophysical risks, including floods. In the United States, the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) publishes static maps² of flood risks. In the United Kingdom, the ‘Check for flooding’³ short-term, operational service provides both alerts (‘flood is possible’) and warnings (‘flood is expected’), including real-time observations. The European Union floods directive aims to manage the flood risk in Europe, including both rivers and coastal risk, by updating flood hazard and risk maps and taking measures to reduce risk.⁴

While the utility of operational alert services is undeniable for saving lives and reducing immediate loss and damage during emergencies, properly addressing the sea level rise driven by climate change necessitates both national adaptation plans ([Perini *et al.* 2016](#)) and long-term territorial planning ([IPCC 2023](#)). For example, [Narendr *et al.* \(2022\)](#) employed an analytical hierarchical process to delineate zones of vulnerability and risk indices for Sagar Island, aimed at informing governmental decision-making and enhancing resilience.

In Italy, territorial planning is articulated at various administrative levels, ranging from the regional to the urban one. Urban planning is conducted through a master plan, known in the Apulia Region as Piano Urbanistico Generale (PUG).

The municipality of Lecce, in Apulia, includes a 20-km-long coastal strip on the Adriatic Sea ([Figure 1](#)). This territory is characterized by a diversity of natural environments and human presence ([Figure 2](#)). Sandy beaches are bordered by dunes and back-dune wetlands. Swamp lands reclaimed in the early 1900s were rapidly and irregularly urbanized in the 1970s and 1980s, exploiting the infrastructure and land grid created by reclamation works ([Curci *et al.* 2022](#), cf. places of interest (POI) #20, #30, #36 and #37 in Supplementary Material file poi.xlsx). This exacerbated the existing geological hazards from both sinkholes and flooding ([Margiotta & Parise 2019](#)). Climate change, with related mean sea level (MSL) rise, may represent an additional threat, with an enhancement of existing hazards ([Hinkel & Klein 2009](#)).

Adaptation strategies identified in the scientific literature span a wide array of options, primarily shaped by governance archetypes ([Bongarts Lebbe *et al.* 2021](#); [Galluccio *et al.* 2024](#)). These range from coastal protection to adaptation and from infrastructure-based to integrated approaches. Hard interventions – such as concrete seawalls – were traditionally favoured, yet they often generate significant ecological impacts and typically fail to offer long-term protection. In contrast, soft adaptations like beach nourishment enhance coastal resilience to extreme sea level (ESL) events, though they rely heavily on the availability of large volumes of suitable sand. Accommodation measures may involve building-specific protections, the development of drainage infrastructure, as well as contingency planning and early warning systems. Managed retreat, involving the relocation of buildings or entire communities inland, sometimes represents the safest option. Despite social, psychological, and financial barriers to acceptance, it is being implemented in pilot projects. In Ravenna, where a vast area is exposed to coastal flooding, two alternative scenarios have been envisioned: one that seeks to preserve the current territorial configuration at all costs, despite rising sea levels, and another that allows the anthropogenic landscape and natural ecosystems to evolve more freely ([Lobosco & Mencarini 2020](#)).

Adapting a territory to sea level rise is a key aspect of long-term urban planning, closely tied to the aims of a PUG. Long-term master plans for Lecce were adopted in 1934, 1960, and 1989. Throughout the last three City Council terms, various efforts were undertaken to revise the plan. A comprehensive version of the PUG was finalized in 2023, receiving a favourable assessment from the Basin Authority in 2024. However, following the most recent elections, the newly appointed Municipal Administration opted to withdraw the PUG to carry out further revisions. The scientific work discussed in this manuscript originates from the public consultation phase conducted during the preceding Council term. To our knowledge, no similar scientific investigations had been carried out in this specific area before. This lack of information could hinder efforts to develop a comprehensive, long-term strategy for safe and sustainable urban development along the coastal strip of Lecce.

¹ <https://www.jma.go.jp/jma/indexe.html>.

² <https://www.fema.gov/flood-maps>.

³ <https://check-for-flooding.service.gov.uk/>.

⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32007L0060>.

Figure 1 | Case study area. (a) The Apulia region (dark grey) in the context of Europe. (b) Close-up with locations of some tide gauges of the Rete Mareografica Nazionale marked by black circles and cells of the gridded products (IPCC, Copernicus, and AdriaClim) used in this work. (c) The territory of the municipality of Lecce, with a highlight of the DTM coverage for its coastal part and the DIVA point (black triangle) used for extracting ESL information and several relevant locations (empty circles) in the coastal territory of Lecce.

To tackle this gap, we conducted a thorough review of the existing data and methodologies, as detailed in Section 2. Based on this review, we identified methods that could be rapidly implemented to provide an initial estimation, as described in Section 3. The significance, constraints, and outlook of our findings are discussed in Section 4, while our conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

2. METHODS

To estimate flooded areas in coastal hazard mapping, two key components are essential: accurate sea level data and a robust methodology for flood assessment. Both components are elaborated upon in the following.

2.1. Sea level information

When characterizing the sea level of a specific coastal region, two primary aspects hold significance: the long-term, time-averaged sea level, commonly termed as MSL, and the episodic, ESL, resulting from high tides, storm surges, and MSL variations. Below, we outline historical observations for MSL and projections pertinent to both MSL and ESL. The projected values for the domain of interest are then provided in Supplementary Table S2.

Figure 2 | Overview map with indication of the POI of PUG's draft (photos for the POIs are linked in the related Supplementary Material file). The colour patches represent the CLC land cover classes and the black lines represent the network of reclamation canals. Local toponyms are represented by horizontally typed names in italics. Each of the eight white-edged sectors, with names angled at 45°, represents an area of 2 km² or 200 hectares (ha).

2.1.1. Mean sea level

In this work, historical sea level data for the coast of Lecce could be obtained from both tide gauges and satellite altimetry. Tide gauges are part of the Rete Mareografica Nazionale, overseen by ISPRA (Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale). They include those located in Bari (145 km away from Lecce) and Otranto (50 km away, as shown in Figure 1(b)). Annual-mean data from these observing stations was obtained from the Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level (PSMSL), which processed the raw data by ISPRA via a Demerliac filter and a weighted average protocol (Holgate *et al.* 2013). Additionally, satellite altimetry gridded data from the Copernicus Marine Service was used in this study. We processed the absolute dynamic topography (ADT variable) of the SEALEVEL_EUR_PHY_L4_MY_008_068 product. This is a daily product with 0.125-degree spatial resolution, which we aggregated on an annual basis. For reducing coastal land contamination of the remotely sensed sea level, the field was averaged on around 50 offshore pixels from the area shown in Figure 1(b). However, we found that the resulting signal does not change much with the extent of the selected region. The MSL global projections were extracted from datasets of the *Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* (IPCC AR5) by Church *et al.* (2013). This gridded product features a one-degree resolution, and the utilized grid point is visualized in Figure 1(b). The AR5 information was downloaded at annual resolution from CEN-UH,⁵ for both the RCP4.5 and 8.5 emission scenarios. The current observed rate of global MSL rise is estimated to be between 3.2 and 4.2 mm/year (IPCC 2023). However, coastal sea level dynamics differ from those of the open ocean due to factors such as bathymetry, coastal geometry, and river discharge (Piecuch *et al.* 2018; Verri *et al.* 2024). Therefore, wherever feasible, global MSL projections should be compared against regionally resolved products.

An MSL projection for the coastal region of Lecce is available as an outcome of the AdriaClim project (Verri *et al.* 2024). AdriaClim is a limited area downscaling from the Med-CORDEX initiative. It includes six model components: atmosphere, land surface, hydrology, marine hydrodynamics, waves, and biochemistry. Rivers ending in the Adriatic Sea and with a catchment area of at least 500 km² were prognostically solved, and their discharges entered the marine hydrodynamics model, while tides and wave feedback were neglected. The hydrodynamics products were provided for the whole Adriatic Sea on

⁵ <https://www.cen.uni-hamburg.de>.

a grid with a 2 km horizontal resolution. The AdriaClim climate simulation started in 1992 and ended in 2050, making use of the RCP8.5 emission scenario. Furthermore, the MSL equation by [Pinaridi et al. \(2014\)](#) was used to estimate the total sea level. In particular, the sea level from AdriaClim was post-processed by adding both a thermosteric and a halosteric contribution accounting for both temperature and salinity anomalies with respect to the reference year (1992). In this work, the resulting total sea level field was averaged on 24 by 24 elemental cells, covering an area comparable to the one used for satellite altimetry, cf. [Figure 1\(b\)](#). The resulting, annual averaged field was considered to represent the regional MSL relevant for Lecce. Its comparison with the global projections is provided in Section 2.1.3.

2.1.2. Extreme sea level

We used ESL projections from [Kirezci et al. \(2020\)](#). They refer to episodic sea level extremes due to a synchronous occurrence of high tide, storm surge, and wave setup. The authors made use of astronomical tides, reanalysis of storm surge, and modelling of wave setup. Long-term stationarity in both waves and storm surge was assumed. The historical extremes were validated by the authors versus observations from the GESLA-2 network, revealing an average root mean square error (RMSE) of about 20 cm. To derive the historical ESL, [Kirezci et al. \(2020\)](#) performed an extreme value analysis. They used a peak-over-threshold approach, fitting with a generalized Pareto distribution and a 98th percentile threshold. For future ESL projections, they incorporated MSL values from the IPCC AR5 projections into their historical estimates. We selected the resulting ESL information at the Dynamic and Interactive Vulnerability Assessment (or DIVA, [Hinkel & Klein 2009](#)) point closest to the region of our interest, shown in [Figure 1\(c\)](#). The data is available for the years 2010, 2050, and 2100, and we interpolated them to an annual resolution using quadratic regression. A centennial return period was used, which equates to a 1% annual probability of occurrence. According to FEMA's classification, this level is deemed 'high-risk', signifying at least a one-in-four chance of flooding during a 30-year mortgage period. Since Lecce's past masterplans remained in place for a similar duration, there is a high probability of experiencing centennial flood events during the time of the next one. To estimate the confidence interval for future ESL, we used the RMSE found by [Kirezci et al. \(2020\)](#) in their validation phase. As in their dataset the wave climate was assumed to remain constant, the primary driver of long-term changes was the rise in MSL.

2.1.3. Comparing sea levels

[Figure 3](#) displays the time series of annual-mean, sea level observations, and projections utilized in this study. The ESL signals are referenced to the vertical datum of the ITALGEO-05 geoid (see Section 2.2.2); the MSL to the 1986–2005 baseline period of the IPCC AR5 projections. As observed in [Martínez-Asensio et al. \(2014\)](#), both tide gauge and satellite MSL observations, along with AdriaClim projections, exhibit significant (order of a few centimetres) interannual variability. Moving on to the

Figure 3 | ESL values from [Kirezci et al. \(2020\)](#) for the RCP4.5 scenario as the dashed black line with a grey band relative to their RMSE; 5–95th quantile range for the IPCC AR5 MSL projections as coloured solid lines (light blue: RCP4.5; light red: RCP8.5); annual-mean MSL from AdriaClim (solid black line), from satellite altimetry (dashed red line), and from tide gauges in Bari and Otranto (yellow and blue markers, respectively). See the text in Section 2.1.3 for the vertical datums.

MSL projections, both their central values and the 5th–95th percentile plumes are considered. They indicate that, depending on the greenhouse gas emission scenario (RCP4.5 or RCP8.5), the study area in Lecce is projected to experience an additional sea level rise of approximately 17–21 cm by 2060, relative to 2020 levels (cf. *supplementa.xlsx* in the Supplementary Material). This increase is expected to proportionally intensify the magnitude of ESL events.

AdriaClim exhibits interannual variability with an amplitude comparable to that observed in satellite altimetry but shows limited temporal coherence with observational datasets. This is expected, as a free-run oceanographic model was employed, meaning that it was not nudged towards observed states. During the 2010–2050 period, the AdriaClim data suggests an average MSL growth rate at Lecce of approximately 3.5 mm/year. This aligns closely with the IPCC AR5 projections, particularly those associated with the RCP4.5 scenario. However, the regional projection of AdriaClim was derived for RCP8.5. The relatively lower trend observed in AdriaClim compared with the global projections for RCP8.5 may be explained by variability in the freshwater budget (Verri *et al.* 2024). Given this observation and recognizing that the ESL by Kirezci *et al.* (2020) incorporates the IPCC MSL projection, we have opted to use their low-emission (RCP4.5) projection. The AdriaClimPlus⁶ project will tackle the challenge of providing more reliable regional-to-local sea level projections for various climate scenarios.

As shown in Figure 3, the ESL at Lecce exceeds the MSL by approximately 60 cm. According to the FES2014⁷ model output, the astronomical tidal range at Lecce is around 26 cm. Therefore, storm surge and wave setup account for most of the episodic sea level rise observed during extreme events. Furthermore, the ESL – MSL value remains constant throughout the projection period, as Kirezci *et al.* (2020) assumed a stationary wave climate, with no anticipated future changes in wave conditions.

2.2. Coastal flooding and modelling

The relevant literature for coastal flooding and modelling is reviewed in Section 2.2.1, before the method used for the estimation of coastal flooding in Lecce is presented in Section 2.2.2.

2.2.1. Literature

Numerical methods for coastal flooding include both hydrodynamic models (HDMs) and bathtub models (BTMs).

HDMs are numerical solvers of the shallow water equations, which represent the conservation of mass and momentum in two or three dimensions. In the past three decades, numerous HDMs have been developed or updated, including: TELEMAC-2D, solving the De Saint Venant equations of free surface flow on an unstructured grid (Galland *et al.* 1991); MIKE 21, a suite simulating hydrodynamics, advection–dispersion, short waves, sediment transport, water quality, eutrophication, and heavy metals (Warren & Bach 1992); XBeach, which includes a non-stationary wave driver for wave-generated surf and swash motion (Roelvink *et al.* 2009); LISFLOOD-FP, coding new equations from 1D shallow water theory, with a sensitivity to soil friction (Bates *et al.* 2010); FUNWAVE, solving a set of fully non-linear Boussinesq equations and which accurately predicted wave runup against a suite of benchmark test data (Shi *et al.* 2012); Delft3D, a multi-dimensional hydrodynamic and transport simulation programme which calculates non-steady flow and transport phenomena resulting from tidal and meteorological forcing; and WRF-Hydro-CUFA, based on the hydrologic model WRF-Hydro and including a hydraulic flow solver, to consider flood controls of stormwater drainage (Son *et al.* 2023).

Instead, BTMs are a class of modelling approaches that compute the intersection between a water surface corresponding to the sea elevation and a three-dimensional terrain model. BTMs do not explicitly incorporate hydrodynamic effects and are therefore considered stationary or static models. They provide a simpler method than HDMs to estimate flood-prone areas and can be computed even within a geographic information system (GIS), at the cost of neglecting water mass conservation and momentum dissipation due to soil friction.

There exists a substantial body of literature discussing the application of BTMs in coastal flood estimation. The paper by Breilh *et al.* (2013) presents a comparison of three flooding methods during the well-documented flooding caused by the Xynthia storm in France. They used BTMs without or with spatially varying sea elevations along the shore and found good predictions for distances from the coastline of the order of hundreds of metres and overestimations at distances of the order of 10 km. Spatial variations of maximum sea level elevation had a limited impact on the estimation of the flooding. In Seenath *et al.* (2016), a BTM was compared with two HDMs (LISFLOOD-FP and TELEMAC-2D) in a tropical sandy coast

⁶ <https://www.italy-croatia.eu/web/adriaclimplus>.

⁷ <https://www.aviso.altimetry.fr/en/data/products/auxiliary-products/global-tide-fes.htm>.

with coral reefs, finding that all three models were consistent (less than 5% difference in flood predictions). However, when hydraulic connectivity was not enforced, the BTM overestimated flooding. The pan-European study by Vousdoukas *et al.* (2016) considered a BTM, LISFLOOD-FP, and a flood intensity index across all coasts of Europe, using a coarse (90 m) terrain model. They found that a BTM with connectivity can overestimate flood extents by 56% compared with LISFLOOD-FP, especially for coasts with low-lying and mild-slope terrain. This approach operates under the assumption of a constant hydraulic head loss, irrespective of terrain slope and roughness. An impressive observational dataset for a specific flood event for a 20 km coastline along an open estuary in eastern Canada was used by Didier *et al.* (2019) to compare the performance of a BTM versus the XBeach model (Roelvink *et al.* 2009). Both models correctly predicted flooded areas, with BTM overpredicting their extent by 36% and the floodwater depth by 0.5 m. The floods that occurred in North Carolina during Hurricane Florence were computed through three variants of BTM in Rucker *et al.* (2021). When compared with a high-resolution, full-physics model, they found that a basic BTM method overpredicts water level extents, while one corrected with a parameterization for head loss (based on Manning's equation) performed better, with close matches to the true flooded areas. In Hong *et al.* (2024), a BTM not accounting for shoreline connectivity and an HDM were compared for a flood event in the Great Lakes. The flooded areas were found to be consistent, with BTM overestimating flooding in not-connected areas. Accordingly, a prevailing consensus in the literature highlights the critical importance of ensuring connectivity for the successful implementation of a BTM. The following subsection outlines the approach adopted to incorporate this principle into our analysis.

2.2.2. Implementation

Given the limited availability of high-resolution input data required for HDMs – such as high-resolution topography, land cover, and soil characteristics – we employed a BTM approach. Despite its simplified nature, this method enabled the efficient identification of flood-prone areas across a substantial stretch of coastline, spanning approximately 15 km and covering an area of 10 km². This extensive spatial coverage offers valuable input for preliminary flood risk assessment and supports strategic planning efforts along the Lecce coast.

To represent the land topography of the coastal strip of Lecce, a digital terrain model (DTM) is used in this work. The DTM is based on data collected from an airborne LiDAR sensor flown in summer 2015. The horizontal resolution was 1 m and the vertical accuracy 30 cm. Besides the DTM, orthorectified aerial photos were used. Land elevations were given in terms of orthometric heights with respect to the ITALGEO-05 geoid (Barzaghi *et al.* 2007). This surface is termed IT-05 in the following.

Additionally, land cover data was employed in this work to provide qualitative insights into the nature of areas susceptible to future flooding. Distinguishing between urban, agricultural, and wetland areas can be pivotal for decision-makers aiming to devise effective adaptation strategies. Notably, Leal-Alves *et al.* (2020) specifically differentiated urban areas from the overall inundated region. In perspective, land cover data can significantly contribute to improving flood modelling methodologies, especially by aiding in the estimation of terrain roughness (Vousdoukas *et al.* 2016; Rucker *et al.* 2021). The land cover classification utilized in the present work is inherited from the original provider, such as Corine or Sentinel-2 (cf. Supplementary Material Section 2). This implied that, for example, the term 'salt marsh' may encompass not only brackish water lagoons but also inland freshwater swamps (e.g. 'Rauccio swamp' in Figure 2) located further from the direct sea influence. Other differences between the land cover datasets are discussed in Supplementary Material Section 2.

The ESL values used in this work were referenced to the Earth Geopotential Model 1996 (EGM-96) geoid by Kirezci *et al.* (2020) by adding a mean dynamic topography (MDT). The used procedure does not mention the possibility that EGM-96 and MDT refer to different ellipsoids. Nevertheless, we assumed that the provided ESL values consistently represent orthometric heights on the EGM-96 geoid. Instead, the topographic information for our region of interest is provided in terms of orthometric heights on the IT-05 geoid. Then, to make ESL and DTM values comparable, a procedure to transform across systems of reference is needed and is documented in Supplementary Material Section 1. In essence, the difference in undulation between the geoids of the two datasets (ESL and DTM) was linearized. Then, the ellipsoidal heights of ESL were referred to the IT-05 system of coordinates. In the coastal strip of Lecce, this local variation resulted in an upward adjustment of the ESL by approximately 2.7 cm. This constant offset was added to all ESL values provided by Kirezci *et al.* (2020).

The orthometric height of ESL, once referred to the IT-05 system, can be directly compared with the terrain elevation from the DTM. Given the sea level η at a specific year t and the terrain elevation z , we conducted the following geospatial data processing via the qGIS open-source software:

Figure 4 | Isoline pruning methodology: just flooded areas connected to the shoreline (yellow isolines) are retained, while the remaining ones (magenta) are pruned. The black solid line represents the shoreline for a sea level of 0.00 metres.

- computation of isolines via the command: `gdal_contour -fl $\eta(t)$` ;
- manual pruning of isolines not topologically connected to the shore, as shown in Figure 4;
- creation of a raster field of the flood depth $\eta(t) - z$;
- use of the isolines from step (b) for clipping the raster of step (c);
- overlay of both aerial photos and road graph using the OSMnx package.

To demonstrate that this procedure remains both reproducible and objective, despite involving some manual intervention, consider the following. Once qGIS computes the isolines, the operator selects the one adjacent to the 0 m contour – typically aligned with the current shoreline and open-ended. Closed isolines, in contrast, indicate isolated areas of lower elevation, disconnected from the shoreline, and thus not susceptible to seawater flooding. Related isolines are manually pruned. Fundamentally, the outcome of this procedure is not driven by significant subjective decisions. The pivotal step – selecting the isoline that borders the coastline – is inherently unambiguous. Although some minor variation may arise in how operators handle some small isolines distant from the shore, the overall methodology remains consistent and replicable, minimizing subjectivity in the results.

As a final methodological note, although this article primarily focuses on the hazard dimension, we include flood depth information ($\eta - z$) as a widely used indicator for estimating direct tangible losses (Chen *et al.* 2024) and, thus, one key component in a vulnerability assessment.

2.3. Validation

To establish a ground truth for coastal flooding of the near-present period, both *in situ* and remote observations are, to some extent, viable options and are described in the following. The use of HDMs is out of the scope of this work.

Figure 5 | Photographic evidence of coastal flooding during storms. The photos were taken: (a) 26 November 2023, 11:35; (b) 26 November 2023, 11:12; (c) 25 February 2024, 11:28; (d) 17 December 2023, 12:06; and (e) 8 December 2024, 12:17. Their locations are provided in Supplementary Figures S3 and S4.

2.3.1. *In situ* observations (photos)

Photographs were taken in the aftermath of some major coastal storms.

Figure 5(a) highlights a site where urban development led to the removal of the dunal ridge (cf. POI #30), resulting in notable coastal erosion. A road is seen where seawater overtopped the structure, progressively washing away the underlying soil and rubble. Figure 5(b) shows an accumulation of marine debris and the emergence of a pathway inland, likely formed by wave-driven transport of material through a low-lying corridor.

In contrast, Figure 5(c) and 5(d) depicts an area where the dune system remains largely intact. The presence of scattered driftwood suggests that storm surges overtopped the dunes. Additionally, vehicles parked near the dunes, as in the photo, have likely contributed to soil compaction. In turn, it may have weakened retrodunal vegetation, increased surface water retention, and slowed post-inundation drainage. In Figure 5(d), the absence of a well-defined berm and the irregular debris distribution indicate that water levels extended farther inland than usual. Importantly, there was no significant rainfall recorded in the days preceding the photo.⁸ Figure 5(e) shows the shoreline being quite close to the stone structure of a watchtower of the 16th century (POI #42), which already appears partially submerged.

In general, all flooded areas visible or implied in the photographs are consistent with our model's predictions. Flooding seen in Figure 5(c)–5(e), already occurs under the 2020's ESL, which implies a complete beach inundation at those locations (cf. Figure 6 and Supplementary Figure S4, and POI #42's photo). In A and B, the BTM projects seawater overtopping road elevations beginning in 2030, rather than since the present-day as observed (cf. Figure 6).

2.3.2. Remote sensing information (NDWI)

To validate the inland extent of the flooding, we turn to satellite imagery.

The Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI, McFeeters 1996) derives water presence from the difference between reflected green and near-infrared radiation. Its reliability is constrained by several factors, including coarse spatial resolution

⁸ <https://protezionecivile.regione.puglia.it/bollettini-pluviometrici>.

Figure 6 | Close-up of model flooding (depth according to the hue of blue) and flooding isoline (orange line) for a portion of the Lecce coast next to the locations of Figure 5(a) and 5(b). The solid black line in the sea is the 0 m elevation contour. Panel (c) provides the topography along the two transects shown in black in (a) and (b). A higher-resolution version of this picture is provided as Supplementary Figure S3.

(10 m), uncertainties in the retrieval algorithm, and the conflation of coastal and pluvial flooding signals. Nevertheless, we used L1C Sentinel-2 data⁹ of NDWI as a preliminary remote sensing data source for validation. Our analysis focuses on imagery for 20 December 2023 – a few days after the photograph shown in Figure 5(d) was taken and, as confirmed by official bulletins, during a period without significant rainfall (in December 2023, in Lecce, it rained just 15.6 mm on the 10th and 10.0 mm on the 14th). Although the exact ESL reached during this specific event is unknown, the nearest tide gauges¹⁰ (both in Otranto and Bari) recorded a peak high in daily MSL on 16 December, followed by a week-long drop by about 20 cm. The outcome of the validation via NDWI is provided in Section 3.2.

3. RESULTS

The outcome of the methodology exposed above is presented starting with a focus on a specific but sensitive sector in Section 3.1, followed by a presentation of the entire coastal strip of Lecce in Section 3.2.

3.1. Spiaggiabella

The Spiaggiabella sector (cf. Figure 2) comprises several distinctive features, including a few kilometres of beachfront, an irregularly but densely urbanized coastal area, two coastal and an inland swamp, remnants of an ancient holm oak forest known as Bosco di Rauccio, and some agricultural land.

The flooding maps for Spiaggiabella are shown in Figure 7. At an ESL of 67 cm above the zero-height of the DTM, corresponding to 2020's ESL value in the RCP4.5 scenario, inundation is already affecting the small lagoon near Porto Empedocle, known by the native appellation 'Fiumicelli' (cf. Figure 2). This is the remnant of a larger natural lagoon extending up to via Portonovo and receiving water from a natural opening in the dune belt. Part of this area has been reclaimed and is presently

⁹ <https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/explore-data/data-collections/sentinel-data/sentinel-2>.

¹⁰ <https://www.mareografico.it/it/stazioni.html>.

Figure 7 | Flooded areas in the ‘Spiaggiabella’ sector during ESL events in selected years of the 21st century: (a) 2020, (b) 2060, and (c) 2040. The orange contour line outlines the flood extent, while flood depth is indicated in shades of blue. The background imagery includes (a) an NDWI map and (b, c) the orthophoto. Panel (d) shows a time series of flooded area by land cover type, using the same colour scheme as in Figure 2. A higher-resolution version of this picture is provided in Supplementary Figure S6.

used as a car parking area. At the termination of via della Gioventù, instead, an entire dune belt was removed to give place to a sports field. The resulting waterproof soil favours seawater advection towards the urban settlements during ESL events. A few hundred metres to the south, another large pond is bordered by urbanized blocks centred around via Rapallo and via Portofino where, following the complete removal of the dunal ridge, houses were built directly on the beach (see Figure 5(a) and 5(b) and the model outputs in Figure 6, as well as POI #30’s photo). A few hundred metres further south, a discontinuity in the dune belt occurs at the convergence of Via Torvajonica and Via Ortona, allowing seawater to intrude inland, as

previously illustrated in Figure 5(c) and 5(d) and Supplementary Figure S4. Figure 7(b) and 7(c) show that, at the higher ESL values projected for 2040 and 2060, all existing seawater inlets extend further inland and eventually merge with one another, as well as with new inlets that have formed since 2020. This could result in the inundation of multiple urban blocks situated along roads that intersect the shoreline, with floodwaters gradually advancing and eventually overtopping the provincial road SP133.

Figure 7(d) shows the temporal evolution of the maximum floodable area and its apportionment by land cover. In the Spiaggiabella sector, a doubling of the flooding extension is anticipated by 2060 with respect to 2020's value. This is mainly due to flooding of urbanized areas (passing from 11 to 20 ha) and expansion of the coastal marshes (exceeding 4 ha, from an initial 0.5 ha, cf. Supplementary Material data).

3.2. Entire coastal strip of Lecce

A comprehensive depiction of computed coastal flooding during ESL events in 2060, which is the envisioned time horizon of the new urban master-plan of Lecce, is illustrated in Figure 8. It is a composition of sectoral maps provided in Supplementary Figures S5–S12. Those results can be critically assessed through comparison with the satellite imagery of NDWI:

- In the Spiaggiabella sector (Figure 7), the most prominent coastal flooding feature is an encroachment originating at Fiumicelli, which poses a potential risk of overtopping the provincial road. Between Via Taormina and Via Ortona, floodwaters emerge from a breach in the dunal ridge (cf. Figure 6).
- Another significant ingress of seawater occurred in the Torre Chianca sector, in the 'Fetida' pond area (Supplementary Figure S8 and POI #39), affecting several roads leading directly to the beach between Via Gorgona and Via Ponza. These flooded areas are captured by the BTM as well. Inundation is also observed further south in the same sector – specifically along Via Pianosa and Via Levanzo – as corroborated by satellite imagery from the event.
- Finally, a third key location is identified in the Frigole sector. According to the BTM, beginning in 2030 (Supplementary Figure S12(d)), a corridor among beach club structures serves as the main entryway for seawater, reaching both the waterfront road (Lungomare Attilio Mori) and the adjacent rural hinterland.

In the remaining portions of the coastal strip under examination, no major encroachments were observed in the NDWI imagery. Noteworthy false positives in the BTM maps appear in the area surrounding the Idume basin and the Acquatina lagoon. This discrepancy may be attributed to the dense reed beds and other lagoonal vegetation present in the area, which are not correctly represented in the DTM. This area is classified as 'salt marsh' in the Corine land cover classification (Figure 2). However, the DTM currently in use is derived from a 2015 survey and may not accurately represent highly dynamic environments, particularly the dune system. Another major false positive in the BTM output appears in the Zona

Figure 8 | Overview map of coastal flooding during 2060's ESL events. Provincial road SP133 is in white, reclamation canals and the Giammatteo River are in black.

Montegrappa sector, where one of the modelled seawater entry points corresponds to the outlet of a reclamation canal (Supplementary Figure S9, close to the watchtower in POI #36), currently obstructed by sediment accumulation, though. Finally, although the Torre Rinalda sector's beach appears entirely flooded under present-day conditions in the BTM output (Supplementary Figure S5), this is not confirmed by the NDWI map for the selected date. This is a false negative, as *in situ* observations show that seawater reached the base of the watchtower and likely covered the remainder of the beach, as suggested by the wood debris and the absence of a berm (see Figure 5(e)).

4. DISCUSSION

The validation data and flood maps from this study highlight that coastal flooding along the Lecce coastline mainly begins with dune breaches. Then, seawater advances into the retrodunal zones or, in areas where dunes have been completely eroded, into human-made infrastructure. Dune breaches often align with the endpoints of roads that run perpendicular to the shoreline (cf. Supplementary Figure S4), facilitating further inland intrusion of seawater. The impact of ESL events varies markedly along different stretches of the coastline, depending on the land use. At sites where dune systems have been removed to accommodate residential development, flooding presents a direct threat to the built infrastructure (roads and houses). In contrast, where dunes remain but exhibit localized degradation and the retrodunal zone has been compacted, flooding tends to manifest as a semi-permanent condition. This not only impedes beach accessibility but also fosters the proliferation of mosquitoes, compounding both environmental and public health concerns.

Even where agricultural land is not directly impacted, the flooding of lagoons currently characterized by freshwater or brackish water is anticipated to intensify salt intrusion into the groundwater, potentially jeopardizing nearby crops. Additionally, the combination of waters with varying salinity levels may hasten the karstification process, leading to the formation of active sinkholes. In turn, sinkholes could result in damage to buildings or even collapse over the course of decades (Margiotta & Parise 2019).

We maintain that a robust observational foundation is essential for identifying viable adaptation strategies for the Lecce coast. The installation of a tide gauge and the establishment of continuous monitoring of hydrometric levels would provide invaluable information. It could improve model reliability through validation data (see Section 2.3) and, potentially, develop early warning systems for coastal flooding. Webcams could be installed along roads terminating in the retrodunal area or directly on the beach to monitor flood extent, providing valuable information for model calibration and validation. We believe that an inclusive, participatory approach, engaging all relevant stakeholders and grounded in robust evidence from empirical observations and model-based simulations, is essential to avoid maladaptive outcomes for the coastal territory of Lecce.

The findings of this work carry significant implications for decision-making across multiple time-scales. In the short term, the generated flood maps can aid in identifying priority areas for targeted mitigation investments. For long-term urban planning in Lecce, these high-resolution maps delineate coastal urban settlements at risk of flooding as well as relatively safer areas. Furthermore, the outputs may support the implementation of disaster risk insurance mechanisms promoted by the Italian National Adaptation Plan for Climate Change.¹¹

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study offers a spatially detailed assessment of projected coastal flooding along the Lecce coastline, grounded in global MSL projections and ESL estimates under the RCP4.5 scenario. By 2060, ESL is anticipated to rise by about 17 cm with respect to the 2020 baseline, prompting the need for localized risk assessments to support adaptation planning. We employed a high-resolution (1 m) DTM and applied vertical datum adjustments to harmonize geophysical references for ESL elevation. Flood extents were simulated using a BTM with enforced shoreline connectivity, and model results were corroborated through *in situ* and remote sensing observations of storm-induced encroachments.

The analysis focused on a 15 km stretch of coastline, with flooding projections extended through 2060 – consistent with the current urban planning horizon. The northern sectors of the Lecce coast, mainly Spiaggiabella, Torre Chianca, and a specific site in Frigole, are most susceptible to coastal flooding. Land-use-based flood classifications highlighted spatial variability in exposure, with critical flood ingress points predominantly associated with breaches – natural or anthropogenic – in the dunal barrier.

¹¹ PNACC, Chapter 4 and Attachment IV – "database azioni".

The study highlights the critical role of a robust observational network, supporting early warning systems and model validation and refinement, and calls for participatory, evidence-based planning to ensure effective and context-sensitive responses. These insights provide essential guidance for both short-term flood mitigation efforts and long-term urban planning and may support broader resilience initiatives for the coast of Lecce.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

G.M.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Project administration, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing; M.L.S.: Writing – review & editing, Data curation, Investigation, Software, Visualization; G.V.: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing; V.S.D.C.: Writing – review & editing, Data curation, Investigation, Software; R.B.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing; and D.C.: Writing – review & editing, Data curation, Investigation.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

DTM and aerial photos were provided by the Municipality of Lecce; AdriaClim data are available from <https://erddap.cmcc-opa.eu/erddap/index.html>; for ITALGEO-05 data, contact R.B. and D.C.; the network of reclamation canals was provided by S. Margiotta; all remaining datasets are available in publicly accessible repositories.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare there is no conflict.

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